

EXPLORERS

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Santa Clara University

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Department of Computer Science and Engineering

Internet of Things Research Lab

scu.edu

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Santa Clara University blends high-tech innovation with a social consciousness. Located in the heart of Silicon Valley, SCU pursues new technology, encourage creativity, engage with our communities, and share an entrepreneurial mindset.

The **SCU IoT Research Lab** from the Department of Computer Engineering focuses on the design and development of low-power wireless communication protocols, edge and fog computing, and software-defined networking. We are primarily interested in mission-critical IoT applications such as medical monitoring and industrial control.

The research lab is collaborating with various companies in Silicon Valley, including Intel, Cisco, Cypress, and Broadcom, to define and develop solutions for real-world problems.. In addition to developing new theoretical concepts and algorithms, we follow an empirical approach towards the design and evaluation of IoT systems.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x3 CHALLENGES

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Manufacturing
Health
Sustainability
Environment
Security

CHALLENGE #5 - SCU-FOG-01

→ Resource Allocation Strategies for Edge/Fog Computing

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

This challenge is focused on allocating the resources of edge/fog nodes to reproduce contained IoT devices based on their processing, memory, and communication demands. To this end, parameters such as the available resources of edge/fog nodes, the available bandwidth of the links between end-devices and edge/fog nodes, and the delay of communication and processing must be taken into account. Designing centralized and distributed mechanisms is therefore necessary to tackle these challenges.

OBJECTIVES

Enhancing the efficiency of resource allocation to meet the desired computational, networking, reliability, and delay requirements of various edge/fog applications;
New software platforms supporting resource allocation in edge/fog networks

SKILLS REQUIRED

Algorithms, SDN, Virtualization, Docker, Kubernetes, OpenFlow

CHALLENGE #6 - SCU-WIRE-02

→ Predictive Scheduling for Wireless Mission-Critical IoT Applications

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Airtime utilization, queueing in multiple layers of the protocol stack, carrier sensing, and many other factors affect the transmission time of packets exchanged between wireless access points and end-devices. In this challenge we employ machine learning techniques to predict packet transmission delay and schedule transmissions according to application demands.

OBJECTIVES

Enhancing the energy efficiency and timeliness of wireless communication in IoT scenarios;
 New machine learning models to predict packet transmission delays;
 Architectures supporting centralized coordination and scheduling of multiple access points;
 Enabling the adoption of 802.11 standards in mission critical applications

SKILLS REQUIRED

Algorithms, Linux kernel, scheduling, machine learning, deep learning, wireless communication, mobility

CHALLENGE #6 - SCU-IOT-03

→ Real-time and scalable protection of IoT devices

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Monitoring and securing IoT devices in a real-time and scalable manner is challenging. For example, since IoT devices are resource constrained, they are more vulnerable against DDoS attacks compared to regular computing platforms such as laptops. This means even a low-rate SYN attack can increase the energy consumption of these devices and could also result in disconnection and device failure. Understanding the impact of various attacks on different hardware architectures, operating system types, and networking protocols stack is necessary to design defense mechanisms. In addition, we employ techniques such as device classification and traffic analysis to design defense mechanisms.

OBJECTIVES

Profiling the operation and vulnerabilities of IoT devices against various types of attacks;
 Novel device classification and traffic monitoring mechanisms;
 Defense mechanisms against various DDoS attacks;

SKILLS REQUIRED

Network security; wireless communication; software-defined networking; machine learning

